

Recommendations from the original mandate of the Job Allocation and Handling WG

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Introduction to the WG

The WG on Job Allocation and Handling was proposed after [presentations and discussions in 2024 WLCG WS](#) concluded this forum was needed. The WG was approved by the October 2024 WLCG Operations Coordination meeting, the WG started its activity in November 2024.

Since the start of the WG activity, 6 topical meetings have been held, attended typically by 5 to 10 participants. These sessions included contributions from members of LHC VOs and large WLCG site experts, such as R. Walker, F. Stagni, F. Barreiro, M. Storetvedt, A. Delgado, B. Jones, M. Kühn, C. Acosta, T. Birkett, O. Smirnova. The group [reported](#) on the status of its activities at the 2025 WLCG Workshop.

Original mandate for the WG

“The goal of the WG is to define the most efficient strategy for job allocation and handling, namely, the most efficient core count for batch job allocation and a more efficient handling of different job classes with diverse requirements. This includes analysis of the experience accumulated so far for running multi-core jobs, whole job scheduling, different approaches for handling jobs with specific requirements, as for example, high-memory jobs. Based on these studies, the recommendations for the sites and LHC VOs should be developed and presented to the community. The WG includes experts from the WLCG sites and LHC VOs.”

Reports from the LHC VOs

ATLAS:

ATLAS employs a mix of pilot modes (push, pull, pilot streaming). Scheduling of ATLAS jobs to the remote resources relies on the LRMS, where they are observed by sites as jobs of diverse core count and memory requirements. This corresponds to the diversity of ATLAS

workload types, diverse in their resource requests. The major workloads run as multi-core, so typically over 80% of the grid cores are used by multi-core jobs. Several workloads are not suitable for multi-core, e.g. merging, and others cannot easily be parallelized (particularly some evgen and most user payloads). Not all scale well to more than 8 processes/threads per job, and only G4 simulation can efficiently use very many cores. There is a diversity in memory/core needs, which the experiment has classified into 4 groups:

- Low memory: 1GB/core
- Standard: 2GB/core
- High memory: 3GB/core
- Very high memory: the maximum defined by the queue.

As remote scheduling depends on the local scheduler, in order to satisfy their need for an overall increased fraction of high-memory slots, ATLAS has implemented an active throttling of the diverse Panda queues targeting a given site in order to tune the average use of memory/core according to the capacity of each of the sites. Indeed, workloads in ATLAS are generally dominated by low memory simulation tasks, at 1 GB. Therefore, by pushing a number of such low memory jobs along with their required high and very-high memory jobs, the overall memory/core metric is kept under control, resulting in low impact on the total number of CPU cores left unused in the remote WNs, even in the case of standard mem/core slots (2 GB).

The overall control is managed from ATLAS per site, but still local scheduling, required to maximize CPU utilization at the WN level, is left to the site admins. This results in a certain fraction of idle cores per WN, which highly depends on the site admins expertise in the scheduling policies employed by their local batch system. This overall utilization inefficiency is only measured at the site and not reports, although there is a certain level of agreement that it should be accounted for in order for the overall utilization metrics in shared multi-VO sites to result in a fair comparison.

This strategy is in general regarded to be a great success, as it results in up to 50k cores in total available for ATLAS at the very high-mem slots category (5 GB/core). Moreover, these slots are available now at a larger group of WLCG sites.

With regards to the ATLAS interest in moving to 16 cores as a new common default, the experiment finds it a trade-off, as advantages are expected (less scheduling at the PANDA queues for the same workload), but potentially some effect on CPU Eff scaling, and throughput, depending on job type. Larger jobs need also be longer (e.g. double events/job) to try and conserve CPU efficiency.

Considering this, moving to 16 cores is not rejected by ATLAS, who has agreed to switching from 8 to 16 cores per multicore job in favor of shared sites keeping a common slot size with CMS and ALICE. In any case, 8-core slots will also be needed for some categories of multicore jobs, along with a certain fraction of single-core slots for certain tasks as well (evgen, merge, analysis...). Again, as the final scheduling of jobs to resources will rely on the remote batch system, the question still is whether such diversity of requests can be co-scheduled together efficiently, and how to measure and account for this inefficiency.

In terms of runtime, 96h is already a standard walltime requirement for ATLAS tasks. Jobs actually are configured mostly to run for 12h, although still some do indeed run for up to 4 days. Finally, concerning whole-node scheduling, ATLAS finds no clear benefit for it in the grid context, although acknowledges it to be a common requirement in many HPC allocations. This makes such resources not suitable for those payloads that can't efficiently scale to larger core counts.

CMS:

The CMS model is based entirely on multicore pilots, technically supported by HTCondor partitionable slots. This makes them suitable for 8/16/other fixed size slots, as well as whole-node slots, both in the Grid and HPC contexts. Internal partitioning of the pilots then deals with the diversity of payload jobs, in a transparent manner to the LRMS. This results in a simplified approach from the sites' perspective, with no need for dedicated high-memory slots. Concerning whole-node slots, they are in fact already in use in multiple sites, generally exclusive to CMS. They are beneficial for CMS as they provide increased scheduling flexibility. The efficient use of whole-node slots is related to extended (beyond 48h) pilot lifetime. The ability to employ whole-node slots for multiple fragmentary payload tasks also represents a solution for the usual WN granularity found in many HPCs.

A campaign was executed in 2025 to switch from 8-core slots at CERN and the European Tier-1s into larger slots. As a result, now 16-core and also whole-node slots have been made available, providing an overall increased flexibility for internal scheduling. An immediate use-case for the capacity unlocked from the new slot sizes has been the execution of Run 3 tier-0 prompt reconstruction jobs (which required in some cases 16-cores) at CERN and a large fraction of resources at the Tier-1s.

According to this expected need in the Tier 0 data reconstruction, the transition to larger slots for CMS started at CERN in mid February 2025, in preparation for the LHC run. A fraction of the resources is being provided as whole-node slots in the dedicated CERN Tier 0 partition, while the slots provided with the shared (Tier 2) farm have been reconfigured from 8 to 16 cores. Longer jobs (96h) are indeed supported, and currently already in use. The case of the Tier 1 sites is similar, with European Tiers-1s (multi-VO) having evolved from 8-core to 16-cores slots, and whole-node slots at the dedicated resources at FNAL.

ALICE:

The ALICE model is well aligned with CMS strategy, being based on similar principles (late-binding, partitionable slots), although deployed with different technologies. ALICE's model rely on local voboxes querying the central WM queues, launching pilot jobs based on the compatibility of the workflows to the sites. Pilots then acquire resources from the local batch systems and pull payloads from the queues. Such local voboxes are easy to maintain and update, and are based on distributed standard container images shared via repo.

Java ALICE Environment (JAlEn) middleware launches multicore pilot jobs capable of executing multiple payloads in parallel. Similar to CMS, a combination of multi-sized, multi-user payloads can be allocated resources at a given multicore slot. Payloads run in nested containers, ensuring software availability for all payloads, and then sub-containers for

process isolation. The fine-tuning of resource utilization is possible where cgroups v2 are supported. This is in fact the preferred option, as singularity (Apptainer) containers do not enforce the strict utilization of allocated resources. Additionally, slot oversubscription is applied dynamically to help regain CPU efficiency in the case of whole-nodes slots.

In terms of preferences, ALICE's position is analogous to CMS. ALICE finds multiple benefits from using large multi-core slots. This includes flexibility in mixing workloads, oversubscription for improved CPU efficiency, as well as GPU brokering. ALICE's model is therefore very suitable, ready, and in favor of moving to larger slots (16-core) and even whole-node (the preferred option) where sites can support it.

LHCb:

In the LHCb case, workloads have been up to now dominated by single-core jobs, therefore the allocation of single-core slots for their tasks already covers the majority of their needs. In fact high memory and multicore jobs represent only a very small fraction of the total workload and there is no expectation for this to change in the short to mid term. LHCb executes mostly MC GEN in the grid, which, even if technically capable of being executed as multi-core, is very efficient in the use of memory. So the execution of such tasks as single core jobs already ensures they will fit within the standard 2 GB/core resources found in the grid.

The LHCb computing team has recently been busy with deploying DiracX in production, which is equipped for the exploitation of multi and large-core nodes, also supporting whole-node allocations. However, in practice, LHCb is still missing the payloads that would require those larger slots. The LHCb software version fully enabling exploitation of multiprocessor jobs is not yet used for large productions. In summary, for LHCb, the provisioning of CPUs in 1, 8 or 16 cores slots would not make much difference, as in every case they would be subsequently partitioned for single core payloads anyway.

Summary of the feedback provided by the participating sites:

The WG has been especially interested in collecting input from shared, multi-VO, sites. In general, the participating sites remarked that they are ready to comply with the diverse VO requirements, in accordance with their pledges, so they will adapt as necessary. But at the same time they presented a warning to the VOs, as the harder to schedule the full mix of jobs becomes, the more unlikely it will be that resources are used optimally. Sites also emphasized that "difficult to satisfy" requests can potentially lead to a severe reduction of overpledged opportunistic usage, from which some VOs are greatly benefiting, as well as impacting the overall utilization of their clusters. Finally, there is agreement that the deployment of resources in dedicated partitions should be avoided in general, even if, exceptionally, they can be supported at particular sites with very large clusters and high and continuous demand (e.g. CERN).

Conclusions of the discussions between VO members and WLCG site representatives:

In general, larger (e.g. 16-core) slots seem not to be a major concern for sites, especially if more than one VO requests them at a given site. A simple switch from 8 to 16 cores will not imply a significantly more difficult or wasteful scenario, as understood by the current common availability of much larger WNs (in number of total CPU cores) in comparison to a decade ago, when multicore slots were first deployed at the WLCG.

Runtime can be extended beyond 48h (and indeed sites in many cases already support this), although some sites discourage VOs from using very long requests, as it reduces the slot turnaround between users, and impacts the flexibility in the use of the resources, potentially limiting the application of scheduling policies enabling slot allocation as “surplus” and “backfilling” strategies, from which some VOs benefit.

With respect to the availability of memory in the compute slots, sites reply that many are already providing in general more than the nominal 2 GB/core. In general, memory is therefore regarded as an abundant resource, and so scheduling is based entirely on CPUs, and not memory saturation. The use of cgroups allows for the control of the actual memory consumption, which is often not correctly predicted. In any case, as explained in the summarized description of the respective VO models, the importance of the availability of high-memory resources has been greatly reduced given that ATLAS’ mechanism to control overall average memory works as intended, while ALICE and CMS take care of memory management within their pilots.

Whole-node slots often require dedicated VO partitions, and therefore only some big sites (or exclusive to a single VO) agree in providing them, as it is emphasized that it reduces the ability for sites to satisfy all their customers, this reducing the benefits that the “fair-share” policies usually provide.

Status update as of May 2026:

During the existence of the WG, in fact, many objectives initially proposed have already been achieved for most VOs, in terms of accessing larger, longer, high-memory slots, to best suit their processing needs.

ALICE reports to be using already 21 sites in whole-node slots, plus 20 with 16 core slots (about 80% of slots in ALICE). Still, they continue to push towards whole-nodes where possible, aiming for at least 16-core or higher at every site. A majority of CPU resources are now within 72hr slots. Can also already benefit from having GPUs in whole-node slots.

CMS is satisfied with the availability of large (and long) slots, specially at key sites: CERN and the Tier-1s already at 16-core or whole-node slots. Whole-node slots are also in use at certain CMS exclusive sites, mostly in the US. There is an ongoing discussion to move the default from 8 to 16 core slots for all resources (that is, for the remaining Tier-2s), but there is no real urgency at the moment, considering the reduced fraction of the total Global Pool they represent. Given the flexible pilot model, with partitionable slots, there is no need for dedicated high-memory slots.

ATLAS has found that sharing sites providing 16-core job slots for CMS has not been a noticeable problem for scheduling. Still, cannot efficiently run most workloads on more than 8 cores, so the default standard remains at 1 and 8 core tasks. Running some 16-core G4 jobs at KIT definitely helps with the local scheduling. Concerning memory, the dynamic scheduling of jobs from 4 different memory/core ranges, is leading to an overall satisfaction for ATLAS' needs.

Concerning a potential move by ATLAS to use a similar model to CMS and ALICE, there is some localized investigation ongoing in the utilization of an overlay batch system (e.g. NHR in Germany), which would provide ATLAS with a similar functionality to the "partitionable slots". Despite ongoing investigation into a potential wider use of such a tool, ATLAS does not find it to be widely needed, with the main impact reserved for the HPC allocation cases (which typically provide slots with a minimal granularity of a whole node).

LHCb model has in practice not changed, as it is still using largely single-core slots, given that simulation software only runs as a multiprocess since the latest version. This is production level ready, but in practice not yet put to use. There is also no need for high-memory slots. Finally, DiracX is capable of handling whole-node scheduling for CPUs (but not for GPUs yet).